

Table SM3. Relative abundance (%) of the ten top taxa of the benthic macrofauna from the continental slope and the São Paulo plateau, in Santos Basin, SW Atlantic, along a depth gradient from 400 to 2400 m. For Annelida: (P) Polychaeta; Crustacea: (T) Tanaidacea, and (I) Isopoda.

400 m	700 m	1000 m	1300 m	1900 m	2200 m	2400 m
Paraonidae (P) 14.6%	Paraonidae (P) 11.7%	Spionidae (P) 13.6%	Spionidae (P) 17.4%	Spionidae (P) 14.6%	Spionidae (P) 15.8%	Spionidae (P) 15.0%
Pilargidae (P) 9.8%	Spionidae (P) 11.7%	Amphinomidae (P) 7.4%	Amphinomidae (P) 7.4%	Cirratulidae (P) 8.1%	Sabellidae (P) 9.6%	Sabellidae (P) 12.7%
Spionidae (P) 7.5%	Cirratulidae (P) 6.1%	Cirratulidae (P) 6.7%	Cirratulidae (P) 5.0%	Paraonidae (P) 5.6%	Cirratulidae (P) 7.0%	Cirratulidae (P) 6.0%
Syllidae (P) 6.5%	Syllidae (P) 5.1%	Paraonidae (P) 6.5%	Colletteidae (Ta) 5.0%	Sabellidae (P) 4.9%	Amphinomidae (P) 3.8%	Ampharetidae (P) 3.5%
Nereididae (P) 5.8%	Colletteidae (T) 3.5%	Syllidae (P) 5.1%	Paraonidae (P) 5.1%	Colletteidae (T) 4.7%	Ampharetidae (P) 3.6%	Hesionidae (P) 3.4%
Cirratulidae (P) 3.8%	Nereididae (P) 3.5%	Colletteidae (T) 4.4%	Syllidae (P) 3.6%	Ampharetidae (P) 4.0%	Hesionidae (P) 3.5%	Paraonidae (P) 3.3%
Orbiniidae (P) 3.7%	Capitellidae (P) 3.3%	Desmosomatidae (I) 3.3%	Ampharetidae (P) 3.6%	Amphinomidae (P) 3.5%	Orbiniidae (P) 3.4%	Desmosomatidae (I) 3.3%
Oligochaeta 3.5%	Ampharetidae (P) 3.2%	Hesionidae (P) 2.9%	Sabellidae (P) 3.4%	Desmosomatidae (I) 3.3%	Glyceridae (P) 3.3%	Oligochaeta 3.3%
Colletteidae (T) 2.8%	Desmosomatidae (I) 2.7%	Capitellidae (P) 2.4%	Typhlotanaidae (T) 3.3%	Sigalionidae (P) 2.8%	Paraonidae (P) 3.1%	Syllidae (P) 2.9%
Anarthruridae (T) 2.5%	Nemertea 2.7%	Sipuncula 2.2%	Sigalionidae (P) 3.0%	Acrocirridae (P) 2.7%	Colletteidae (T) 2.8%	Sipuncula 2.7%